

APPLICATION OF WATERJET WITHOUT ABRASIVES TO SURFACE TREATMENT OF CFRP

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ABSTRACT

Cutting of FRP by waterjet is widely developed recently. In this study, another new application of waterjet was considered in the field of composites. Surface treatment of CFRP by waterjet was tried to prepare painting and to repair. Nozzle of waterjet was different from usual, like a slit, by which waterjet was ejected in a fan shape.

Materials tested were thermoset and thermoplastic plastic matrix CFRP and some resin panels. Fan type waterjet was ejected to test panels. Parameters were water pressure, nozzle travel speed and work distance etc.

Mainly visual observation was conducted, and when surface was abraded, thickness change was measured, then painting test and trial of repair was conducted.

Following results were obtained.

- (1) Abrading and grinding of surface was occurred by the ejection of fan shape waterjet. Abraded width was controlled by the work distance. This abrading and grinding became large with increase of water pressure, with decrease of nozzle travel speed and with decrease of work distance. There was a certain threshold energy of water flow to begin to abrade surface.
- (2) In the case of the test of PA66 matrix CFRP, proper waterjet process condition was obtained by which abrading of only surface layer resin without damaging the fiber was enabled.
- (3) In the case of the test of epoxy matrix or PPS matrix CFRP, it was difficult to obtain the condition of abrading only resin of surface layer. Removal of both resin and fiber was occurred at the same time, and caused thickness change.
- (4) Repair experiment of composites was conducted by this abrading and grinding method, and it was found the possibility of promising method.

1 INTRODUCTION

Application of CFRP shows the rapid and wide progress from aerospace to automobile and general industrial equipment. One of remained problems is surface treatment to paint or adhesion. CFRP is usually fabricated in the mould, strong release agent is used. It may be attached to the surface of CFRP and it is difficult to be removed, so it might cause a state in which paint does not adhere properly. Now, sanding is applied manually as a pretreatment for painting.

In order to develop mechanized and effective pretreatment process, authors have been studying the application of laser scanning, ozone exposure treatment and waterjet scanning process[1]. In this study, surface treatment by scanning of fan type waterjet was examined. And it was found to grind CFRP panel by this method during experiment. Development of repair of CFRP is also important problem, so trial study to apply preparation of repair by this method was conducted.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Materials

Some resin panels were used to examine basic effect of the scanning of fan type waterjet on surface condition. These were PA66, epoxy, acrylic and PPS etc. Then thermoset resin and thermoplastic resin matrix CFRP were examined. Used materials were shown in Table 1.

Material		Remarks	
Resin	PA66	4~6 mm thickness	
	Polyethylene		
	Acrylic		
	PPS		
	Epoxy		
CFRP*1	PA66 matrix	Woven	Tencate Cetex
	PPS matrix	Woven	Tencate Cetex
	Epoxy Matrix	Unidirectional	KMS6115 by KHI
		Woven	KMS6115 by KHI

*1 1.3~4mmt

Table 1: Materials used

2.2 Waterjet equipment and process

Used waterjet equipment was Mash 3 fabricated by FLOW co. and fan type nozzle which orifices was in slit was used. Maximum water pressure was 414Mpa. The jet stream in the case of using this nozzle was shown in Fig.1 as compared with the conventional nozzle. When ejected nozzle of waterjet was slit, shape of waterjet was as fan, so attack area of waterjet on work surface was thin rectangular shape, and width of jet became wider with increase of work distance.

Nozzle travel speed and water pressure and work distance were controlled as cutting parameter. Abrasive was not used to prevent contamination of the surface. From here, fan type water jet was called as fan jet.

Fig.1: Comparison of conventional waterjet and fan type waterjet used in this experiment

2.3 Measurement

Following measurements were conducted and effect of process parameters on them was considered.

- Macroscopic and microscopic observation of surface of scanned area
- Roughness of surface
- XPS analysis for typical case
- Grinded thickness when surface was severely abraded.

2.4 Trial of application to repair

When resin was hard, it was found that carbon fibers and resin was abraded together, and grinded thickness could be controlled. So trial of application to repair was considered. Step-like scribing was carried out. Then prepreg was layered and cured.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Effect of process parameters and material properties on the surface morphology of scanned resin panel surface.

Fan jet was scanned on several resin panels, and effect of parameters and materials on the surface morphology of scanned area was examined.

When low water pressure, high scanning speed and long work distance was applied, there was no effect on the scanned surface. However these parameters were changed to higher water pressure and/or lower scanning speed and/or shorter work distance, surface morphology became changed. Large difference of effect was shown between soft-tough resin and hard resin.

Fig.2 shows the comparison of scanned area of fan jet between PPS as hard resin and PA66 as soft-tough resin. When work distance was decreased, width of scanned area became narrow. Test condition was written as water pressure (P), nozzle travel speed (V), width of scanned area (W).

In the case of PPS, scanned area was abraded and grinded, and depth of abraded depth was increased with increase of water pressure, with decrease of nozzle travel speed and with decrease of width of scanned area. Results of epoxy resin and acrylic was similar to this results.

In the case of PA66, many short fibers were appeared as hair transplantation on the scanned area. Area of certain thickness might cut and abraded, however resin was not completely cut off from the base panel because of its tough properties. Results of polyethylene resin was similar to this results.

Fig.2: Comparison of the morphology of scanned area by fan jet between PPS and PA66 resin
(Test condition: PPS P=350MPa, V=50mm/sec. W=14mm)
PA66 P=200MPa, V=50mm/sec. W=14mm)

Effect of parameters on the abraded and grinded depth of material was considered. Relation between P and amount of water flow (F) is shown in Equation 1. Water ejection energy (E) per unit area of fan jet scanned area is considered as Equation 2.

$$F = K\sqrt{P} \quad (K : \text{Constant}) \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

$$E = 1/2 \cdot MF^2/(V \cdot W) = G \cdot P/(V \cdot W) \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

(E: Energy of water flow per unit scanned area, M:Mass of water, V : Travel speed of nozzle, W : Width of scanned area, M:Mass of water)

E and P/(V · W) are in a proportional relationship, so from here, $E=P/(V \cdot W)$ was treated as representing the energy of water flow per unit scanned area.

Fig.3 shows relation between energy of water flow (E) and the abraded and grinded depth of PPS panel. Threshold energy was required to start grinding. Then the grinded depth was increased linearly with increase of E above threshold value.

In the case of soft-tough resin, grinded depth could not be defined clearly, however similar effect of energy on the disturbed depth could be seen in which resin was transformed to short fiber.

Fig.3: Relation between energy of water flow and grinded depth of PPS panel

3.2 Effect of fan jet on the morphology of composites

Fig.4 shows the effect of fan jet scanning on the morphology of PA66 matrix CFRP. When the energy of water flow was low, no effect could be seen (Lower case). Energy was increased, rough surface was appeared (Middle case), then roughness was increased with increase of water energy, however carbon fiber layer was not damaged under certain energy (Upper case). So only resin surface was selectively roughened. When this kind of surface was used, paint was very strongly attached.

Fig.4: Effect of the scanning of fan jet on the surface morphology of PA66 matrix CFRP (Area between 2 arrows was scanned)

Fig.5: Effect of the scanning of fan jet on The surface morphology of epoxy matrix CFRP (Area between 2 arrows was scanned)

Fig.5 shows the effect of fan jet scanning on the morphology of epoxy matrix woven fabric CFRP. When energy was low (Lower case), no effect could also be seen. Energy was increased, resin surface is locally removed, then removed area was increased with increase of water power, however original surface was remained discontinuously. Even if the surface was almost rough as shown in the middle case, original surface was remained when viewed microscopically. Abrading of carbon fiber area was started suddenly at certain ejection energy of water flow (Upper case). Then grinded depth was increased with increase of energy of water flow. Similar results was obtained in the experiment of PPS matrix CFRP.

Presence of fluorine on the epoxy matrix CFRP was confirmed by XPS analysis. It might be derived from releasing agent from mould, which inhibited the adhesion of the coating material. It was also detected from the remaining original surface of discontinuously abraded surface. So, proper condition could not be found to remove the resin on the surface without damaging the carbon fibers when matrix resin was hard.

Effect of several parameters on the grinded depth of CFRP was examined. Fig.6 shows the effect of work distance on the grinded depth of epoxy matrix unidirectional CFRP at same fan jet condition. When work distance was increased, width of fan jet at specimen surface was increased. Direction of fan jet scan was along to fiber direction. Grinded depth was large when work distance was small, On the contrary, it was small when work distance was large. Grinded depth at central position was relatively smaller than that of end position when viewed in cross section. Difference of thickness was decreased when work distance was large.

Fig.6: Effect of work distance on the grinded depth of CFRP by fan jet

Fig.7 shows the effect of $E (=P/(V \cdot W))$ on the grinded depth of epoxy matrix CFRP. Threshold energy was also required to start grinding. Then the grinded depth was increased linearly with increase of E above threshold value. Grinded depth of parallel scan direction to fiber was relatively smaller than that of perpendicular scan direction to fiber direction, then that of 45 degree scan direction to fiber direction was between the results of parallel and perpendicular direction. And these value was close when work distance became large.

3.3 Application to repair

Grinding of CFRP by fan jet might be considered to apply the preparation of the repair of CFRP instead of mechanical grinding. Recent waterjet power equipment and jet scanning system becomes sufficiently small to convey the site on the track. This method has some strong points compared with mechanical subscribing as follows.

Fig.7: Effect of water ejection energy on the grinded depth of epoxy matrix CFRP

- a. Dust does not be occurred.
- b. Rigidity request of fixture is considerably relaxed.
- c. Lamination work is easy because stepwise grinding is realized
- d. Mechanical control of process may be applied easily in the future

Trial of repair experiment was conducted for epoxy matrix CFRP. Thickness of the panel was 3.6mm, which was grinded to 3 stepwise cross section. Results of grinded section was shown in Figure 8. Applied fan jet condition was shown as follows.

Area A: (P=200MPa, V=15mm/sec, W=10mm) 2 times repeated

Area B: (P=200MPa, V=15mm/sec W=10mm) 4 times repeated

Area C: (P=200MPa, V=15 mm/sec W=10mm) 5 times repeated then blended

Each step was sufficiently flat and no crack could not be caused at the edge of step. Then joint was fabricated by filling the laminate at stepwise area and cured in a conventional repair process. Tensile strength after repair was sufficiently good.

Fig.8: Grinded panel of CFRP by fan jet to prepare for repair

4 CONCLUSIONS

Fan jet without abrasives was tried to be applied to surface preparation for painting or adhesion. Effect of the scanning of fan jet on the surface morphology of several materials was examined. Materials were resin panels and CFRP panels.

Results were as follows

- (1) Abrading of surface was occurred by the ejection of fan jet. Abraded width was controlled by the work distance. When hard resin panel, for example, PPS or epoxy was used as test material, surface was abraded and then grinded. This abrading and grinding became large with increase of water pressure, with decrease of nozzle travel speed and with decrease of work distance. Grinded depth was

dependent on the energy of water flow per unit scanned area. There was a certain threshold energy of water flow to begin abrade surface. When soft and tough material as PA66 was tested, many short fibers were appeared as hair transplantation on the scanned area.

(2) In the case of the test of PA66 matrix CFRP, proper fan jet process condition was obtained by which abrading of only surface layer resin without damaging the fiber was enabled. And treated surface was good for pretreatment of painting or adhesion.

(3) In the case of the test of epoxy matrix or PPS matrix CFRP, it was difficult to obtain the condition of abrading only resin of surface layer. Abrading of resin and fiber was occurred at the same time, and caused grinding to thickness change.

(4) Work parameters to get almost homogeneous thickness change was obtained. This grinding method was applied of the pre-process of repair. Repair experiment of composites was conducted, and found the possibility of promising method.

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